

Consequences of new technology

Understanding recommended rice cultural practices as related to farmer adoption

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Effective utilization of a new technology demands that users understand the principles behind the technology. This study investigated the relationship between understanding the principles of recommended rice cultural practices and their adoption by farmers.

Rice is the main grain crop of Kerala State, representing more than 35% of the cropped area. In Mavelikara and Karthikappally taluks of Alleppey district, 125 randomly selected rice farmers were the respondents — 60 were contact farmers visited by extension workers on regularly scheduled days and 65 did not have regular extension contacts. A knowledge test related to principles of practices was developed, standardized, and administered to the respondents. Farmers were grouped

Table 1. Zero order correlation between understanding principles and adopting practices n = 120 (60 + 60).

Farmer group	Correlation coefficient
Contact farmers	0.860**
Noncontact farmers	0.888**

**Significant at 0.01 level of probability.

Table 2. Association between understanding principles and adopting practices by the contact farmers (n = 60).

Level of understanding	Contact farmers	
	High adoption	Low adoption
High	25	4
Low	9	22

$\chi^2 = 19.67^{**}$, significant at 0.01 level of probability.

as having high or low understanding based upon the mean knowledge score. The same procedure was used to rate adoption score, based on the mean adoption score of nine cultivation practices.

Zero order correlations between understanding of principles and cultural adop-

Table 3. Association between understanding principles and adopting practices by the non-contact farmers (n = 65).

Level of understanding	Noncontact farmers	
	High adoption	Low adoption
High	20	8
Low	12	25

$\chi^2 = 21.37^{**}$, significant at 0.01 level of probability.

tion were calculated. For both farmer categories the correlation coefficient between understanding the principles and adoption were highly significant (0.860 for contact farmers and 0.888 for non-contact farmers) (Table 1).

A χ^2 test was also used to establish this relationship. Significant χ^2 values showed a strong association between understanding and adoption for both groups of farmers (Tables 2 and 3).

The results confirm that when principles of practice are emphasized with strong procedures of the practice, farmers can easily adopt the practice. □

Announcements

IRRI scientist recognized

F. N. Ponnampereuma received the 1983 Honorary Fellow Award from the Crop Science Society of the Philippines, and the 1983 American Society of Agronomy Fellows Award.

Ponnampereuma has been with IRRI since 1961 and is head of the Soil Chemistry Department. He is the author of many scientific and review papers and is well known for his review "The Chemistry of Submerged Soils," in *Advances in Agronomy* 1972, which has been identified as one of the most cited articles in that field.

De Datta receives award

S. K. De Datta, head of the IRRI Agronomy Department, has been presented with the 1983 Achievement Award for Crop Science Research by the Crop Science Society of the Philippines. De Datta came to IRRI as an agronomist in 1964 and is the author of *Principles and practices of rice production* and many scientific articles and reviews. □

Hooker award

B. Venkateswarlu, senior plant physiologist, All-India Coordinated Rice Improve-

ment Project, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, has been given the biennial Hooker Award for 1982 in recognition of his contributions in rice physiology. The award is given for outstanding contributions in agriculture, animal sciences, and fisheries in India. □

International course on seed technology for vegetable crops

The seventh and eighth international courses on seed technology for vegetable crops will be held at the University of the Philippines at Los Baños (UPLB) 13 Jan-18 Apr 1984 and 14 Aug-31 Oct 1984.